

**MARINE POLLUTION IN THE BLACK SEA DUE TO MINING ACTIVITIES:
PRELIMINARY ENVIRONMENTAL CHARACTERISATION AND RISK
ASSESSMENT**

A. Kontopoulos*, K. Komnitsas, A. Peppas, M. Cambridge, C. Hallett, C. Payne, S. Groudev, I. Spasova, A. Angelov, P. Georgiev, I. Lazar, A. Voicu, S. Dobrota, I.G. Petrisor, M. Stefanescu, D. Georgescu, M. Popescu

**Author for correspondence. National Technical University of Athens, Laboratory of Metallurgy, GR 157 80, Zografos*

ABSTRACT

The intensive mining and ore processing activities in coastal areas in Bulgaria and Romania have resulted in the production of millions of tones of mining wastes and tailings that are characterised as radioactive, toxic and hazardous. Mobilisation and transportation of heavy metals and radionuclides from these sources by a number of physicochemical mechanisms have resulted in widespread contamination of the surrounding soils as well as the Black Sea. In the present paper the main sources of pollution that are currently directly or indirectly affecting the Black Sea were identified and characterised. A risk assessment was performed on a source-pathway-target basis to assess the environmental risks associated with mining wastes at four case study sites. The aim of the assessment was to provide a scoping study to identify the targets and objectives for research into preventative and remedial methods of mine waste rehabilitation. A rehabilitation strategy was proposed for all affected areas, aiming at deactivating the pollution sources and rehabilitating the contaminated areas.

1. INTRODUCTION

Marine pollution in the Black Sea is caused by a number of various activities from neighbouring countries as well as from the transfer of several pollutants by a number of important rivers. Intensive mining and ore processing activities over the last fifty years, in coastal areas in Bulgaria and Romania, have resulted in the production of millions of tones of mining wastes and tailings that are characterised as radioactive, toxic and hazardous. These wastes, that have been deposited in coastal areas often without pre-treatment and do not comply with the environmental standards for safe deposition, have resulted in widespread contamination of the neighbouring soils and the Black Sea due to a number of mobilisation and transportation mechanisms.

In this paper the main sources of pollution that are currently directly or indirectly affecting humans, soils, freshwater ecosystems and the Black Sea, at the areas of Vromos Bay, in Bulgaria (Fig. 1), Navodari and Baia close to Constanta, and Somova close to the Danube Delta in Romania (Fig. 2) were identified and characterised. A fourth area, named Rosia Poeni, in Romania, has also been characterised at an experimental stage.

In order to assess the risk that these tailings pose to the entire ecosystem in these areas, a detailed sampling procedure was carried out involving (Kontopoulos, 1997; Kontopoulos et al., 1996a, 1996b): collection of surface and drill core samples; determination of several geochemical parameters of the tailings; monitoring of pore water level and quality through piezometers installed in drill holes; sampling of surface streams and decant water on a regular basis and study of the naturally existing bacteriological groups. Drill core samples were sub-

jected to chemical and mineralogical analysis, determination of their acid generation potential by using static tests (acid-base accounting) and determination of their toxicity using the EPA TCLP test. Several samples were subjected to leaching by EDTA to determine the bioavailable fraction of toxic metals; a limited number of samples was also subjected to sequential extraction procedure to determine the speciation of heavy metals. The bioavailable fraction of the toxic elements was checked against the Netherlands and the Canadian guidelines for soils as well as the local guidelines and the toxicity of the spoils was compared against the toxicity limits set by the TCLP test. Surface and pore water quality was monitored and checked against existing effluent standards in each country. Radioactivity measurements were also conducted and concentration of radionuclides in tailings, decant water, surface streams and soils were compared against the local standards. The ability of the indigenous microorganisms to solubilise heavy metals and radionuclides was examined in detail. Finally, the mechanisms active in natural wetlands for the purification of surface streams containing heavy metals and radionuclides were studied.

A risk analysis on a source-pathway-target basis was undertaken in order to assess the level of risk posed by each source for each case study area. A rehabilitation strategy will be developed for all affected areas, aiming at deactivating the pollution sources and rehabilitating the contaminated areas with preventative and remedial actions.

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE SITES

Vromos Bay, BG

Vromos Bay is located approximately 12 kilometres E-SE of Burgas city and forms a secondary bay within the larger Burgas Bay at the western shore of the Black Sea. The beach at Vromos Bay, with a maximum width of 200 metres, extends over approximately 3 kilometres in E-W direction, covering an area of approximately 200000 m².

The beach of Vromos Bay has been contaminated by approximately 8 million tonnes of tailings from the nearby located Rossen flotation plant, which produces copper concentrates. The flotation tailings were discharged to Vromos bay between 1954 and 1977 shifting the shore line by up to 150 m into the sea. Since that period, tailings were redistributed by wave and wind action as well as by sea currents. At present, approximately 700000 tonnes of subaerially disposed tailings extend over a beach length of about three kilometres covering an area of approximately 20 hectares. These tailings contain, besides copper and iron minerals, other heavy minerals that carry uranium, radium, thorium and other radionuclides.

Navodari, RO

Navodari is situated in the north vicinity of Siutghiol Lake, on the isthmus between this lake and Tasaul Lake. This isthmus is also a marine coast situated at the mouth of Casimcea valley. The chemical complex which operates at Navodari, covering an area of 15 ha W of Navodari town, was built between 1957-1959, and consists of two plants: one for the production of sulphuric acid and the other for the production of superphosphates. The distance between the chemical plant and the Black Sea is 3 km.

The treatment of phosphates for the production of phosphoric acid has resulted in the production of millions of tonnes of phosphogypsum and pyritic cinders. Phosphogypsum has been deposited in three dumps (stacks); two of them were formed during the periods 1960-1975 and 1975-1996, over an area of approximately 40 ha, contain over 3000000 m³ of phosphogypsum and today are covered partially with spontaneous vegetation. The third decantation pond is under operation since 1996 over an area of 10 ha. Pyritic cinders, with a volume of 975000 m³, have been deposited on a single dump also in the vicinity of the plant. In addi-

tion, decant water from the operating pond, sometimes without neutralisation, is discharged with a pipeline to the Black Sea.

Baia, RO

Baia is situated 45 km N of Navodari and at about 1 km distance from Golovita lake which is connected to the Black Sea. In Baia operates a flotation plant which processes copper ores from Altan Tepe mine which is located at about 10 km N-W of the site.

The tailings from the flotation plant have been deposited since 1965 in three decantation ponds (dumps) situated at a distance of about 500 m from the plant. Two of them were constructed in the periods 1965-1992 and 1992-1996, cover an area of over 100000 m² and contain over 1200000 t of tailings. The third one is under operation since the second half of 1997 over a surface of 2.5 ha.

Somova, RO

Somova is situated 12 km W of Tulcea town, on the right lake side at the start of the extended Danube delta. Mining activities commenced in 1957 with mining and processing of baryte and complex sulphidic ores (chalcopyrite, sphalerite, galena and pyrite) and ceased in 1991.

The resulting tailings, have been deposited in four dumps at the banks of Somova Lake. The first two were formed between 1957-1977 and contain over 1100000 t of tailings, while the third and fourth one were formed between 1978-1991 and contain over 1500000 t of tailings.

Rosia Poeni, RO

At Rosia Poeni, which is situated in the Carpathians, in central Romania, exist three decantation ponds receiving effluents from the nearby located copper flotation plant. Tailings are discharged to the main pond a 1:2.5 tailings:water ratio. Leachates from copper dumps characterised by low pH and high loads of heavy metals are also entering the main decantation pond. The other two, which are emergency ponds, contain smaller quantities of copper tailings.

3. METHODOLOGY

The following methodology was applied for the environmental characterisation of the pollution sources, soils and waters (Kontopoulos et al., 1995):

Sampling was carried out according to a properly designed strategy. Surface and low depth samples were collected using a mechanical excavator; drillcore samples were taken from deeper horizons.

Chemical and mineralogical analyses. Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (AAS) and a LECO Sulphur Analyser were used for elemental analyses. XRD combined with optical microscopy and SEM techniques were applied for mineralogical analyses.

Measurements of geotechnical characteristics of spoils. They include particle size distribution, permeability, wet bulk and true density, and were performed either in situ or in the laboratory.

Determination of the Net Neutralisation Potential (NNP), according to the commonly used acid base accounting technique for the estimation of the potential of the tailings for acid generation.

Application of the Toxicity Characteristics Leaching Procedure (TCLP), for the characterisation of spoils in terms of toxicity.

Determination of the phytoavailable fraction of heavy metals, through leaching with EDTA.

Application of the sequential extraction technique, for the evaluation of the metal speciation and potential mobilisation under various environmental conditions.

The radioactivity of solid samples was measured by a low level background gamma-spectrophotometer ORTEC. The specific activity of Ra-226 in liquid samples was measured using a 10 litre ionisation chamber. The total β -activity was measured by a low background equipment UMF-1500M.

Monitoring of the level and quality of pore water was done with the use of piezometers installed in the drillholes.

The ability of the indigenous microorganisms to solubilise different heavy metals and radionuclides from the flotation tailings was determined by leaching 30 kg of fresh solid samples in plastic lysimeters using as leach solutions natural waters from each area.

4. RESULTS

The characteristics of the tailings, soils, leachates and pore water in Vromos Bay are presented in tables I and II. The analysis of these data reveals the following:

- The tailings at the tailings dam are quite fine and contain low levels of residual sulphides. Their potential for generating acidity and their toxicity according to the TCLP test are considered low. The bioavailable fraction of Pd, Zn and Cu is considered substantial. Pore water analysis within the tailings shows minimum dissolution of heavy elements. The specific activity of the radionuclides (especially U-238 and Ra-226) is considered high.
- The tailings on the beach show a quite normal size distribution due to the leaching action of the sea currents and they contain elevated concentrations of residual sulphides and heavy metals. Because of the sea action their potential for generating acidity and their toxicity according to the TCLP test are considered extremely low. Also, the bioavailable fraction of Pd, Zn and Cu has been decreased. The specific activity of the radionuclides shows elevated values.
- Soils between the tailings dam and the beach are characterised by concentrations of heavy metals and radionuclides which sometimes exceed the Bulgarian standards set for agricultural use of soils.
- Two surface streams which carry mainly all leachates from the tailings dam enter Vromos bay. These streams are characterised by neutral-alkaline pH values, low concentration of heavy metals and high concentration of anions (chlorides and sulphates) and radionuclides. The high concentration of chlorides and sulphides in these streams is mainly due to the use of sea water in the flotation circuit. The streams are also characterised by elevated concentrations of dissolved oxygen and total dissolved solids. The presence of higher concentrations of toxic metals and radionuclides locally in both streams is associated with the activity of several existing groups of heterotrophic bacteria. The solubilisation of heavy metals is attributed mainly to the microbial production of organic acids. Iron and manganese however, are solubilised as a result of enzymatic reduction of Fe^{3+} and Mn^{4+} to the relevant bivalent forms. Toxic metals can be solubilised also from the sulphide minerals with the action of chemolithotrophic bacteria. These bacteria oxidise sulphide minerals by removing the passivation film of S^0 from the mineral surface as a result of chemical, electrochemical and biological processes. Uranium is leached with the following two mechanisms. According to the first mechanism, microbial production of peroxide compounds can oxidise U^{4+} to U^{6+} which is then solubilised as uranyl carbonate or forms complexes with organic com-

pounds present in water. The second mechanism is connected with the microbial secretion of organic metabolites, mainly organic acids, which form complexes with uranium.

Table I: Characterisation of Vromos Bay tailings and soils

	Tailings on beach					Tailings dam				Soils
	<i>Bulgarian Standards for soils</i> mg/kg (average)	Chem. Anal. mg/kg (average)	Specific Activity Bq/kg (average)	TCLP test mg/l	Bioav. fraction mg/kg	Chem. Anal. mg/kg	Specific Activity Bq/kg	TCLP test mg/l	Bioav. fraction mg/kg	Chem. Anal. mg/kg (average)
Cu	280	3458		1.6	142.2	1760		5.5	154	2218
Pb	80	220		0.05	29.1	515		0.9	115	141
Zn	370	164		0.4	12.2	502		2.4	34.9	110
Cd	3	12		0.003	0.12	4		0.01	0.2	9
Co		314				35				96
U	50	100				83				30
S (%)		3				0.8				1.7
Fe (%)		41				10				12
SiO ₂ (%)		19.6				49				45.1
CaO (%)		2.9				7.2				6
MgO (%)		2.1				3.4				3.6
U-238 (Bq/kg)	800		1255				1060			410
Ra-226 (Bq/kg)	800		2725				1115			1160
Th-232			20				17			16
Pb/Bi-214			1835				1020			480
Pb-210			1005				630			210
K-40			435				625			440
NNP (kg CaCO ₃ /t)			555				58			37
Bulk density (g.cm ⁻³)			1.9				1.6			1.5
Wet bulk density (g.cm ⁻³)			1.7				1.6			1.4
Particle density (g.cm ⁻³)			3.8				2.9			2.8
Total porosity (%)			43.1				41.5			44.2
Permeability (cm/s)			1.2x10 ⁻²				2.5x10 ⁻⁴			2.6x10 ⁻³
Particle size analysis (mm)										
+0.25			32.8				9.1			36.6
-0.25+0.125			61.8				13.2			8.6
-0.125			5.4				77.7			54.8

- The quality of the water in the natural wetland existing close to the bay and receiving part of the water of the streams is improved and this is mainly attributed to the physicochemical reactions occurring in a wetland which aid in water purification (Komnitsas, 1994; Brodie, 1993; Davison, 1993).
- Sea water quality (in contact with the beach tailings) is similar to the quality of both streams entering the bay.

The characteristics of the tailings and decant/surface waters in the Romanian sites are presented in tables III and IV. The analysis of these data shows the following:

Navodari

- Phosphogypsum tailings are characterised by low-neutral paste pH values and contain elevated concentrations of sulphur, lead, cadmium and radionuclides. The main concern from the radioactivity associated to Ra-226 is the emanation of radon-222 gas. Although their toxicity according to the TCLP test and their bioavailable fractions are considered low, solubilisation of heavy elements and radionuclides is favoured by local weather conditions. In addition, a great number of microbial communities involved in metals solubilisation and biosorption processes was isolated from phosphogypsum and cinders dumps and from decant waters.

Table II: Characterisation of leachates and pore water in Vromos Bay

	<i>Bulgarian Standards for waters mg/l</i>	Main Stream (mg/l)	Secondary stream (mg/l)	Natural Wetland (mg/l)	Sea Water (mg/l)	Tailings dam pore water (mg/l)
pH	6-9	7.7-9.5	7.1-8.2	7.1-7.5	8-8.3	6.3-8.0
Eh		28-140	41-77	31-127	64-132	-80-(+214)
Dissolved O ₂	2	5.6-9.7	6.8-8.8	3-5.5	8.8-11.3	0.6-1.9
T.D.S	1500	4600-28000	3200-18000	800-3700	17000	880-13200
Cl ⁻	400	1200-15000	1050-12000	460-2300	9000	8800
SO ₄ ²⁻	400	164-3280	440-1700	125-440	1200	188-3350
NO ₃ ⁻	20	2-4.6	n.d	n.d	n.d	
PO ₄ ³⁻	2	0.1-1.4	0.1-0.7	0.2-0.9	0.1-1.4	
Pb	0.2	n.d-0.1	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d-0.1
Fe	5	0.1-2.8	0.1-2.8	0.1-3.5	0.01-0.12	0.1-3.8
Zn	10	n.d-0.5	n.d	n.d	n.d	0.1-16.8
Mn	0.8	0.07-0.14	0.1-0.8	0.08-0.9	0.01-0.08	0.1-13.16
Cu	0.5	0.02-0.9	0.02-0.6	0.01-0.5	n.d	n.d-0.15
U	0.6	0.5-4.1	0.3-3.2	n.d	n.d	n.d
Ra-226 (Bq/l)	0.15	0.03-0.6	0.03-0.55	n.d	n.d	
COD	100	62-284	80-215	64-158	35-82	
BOD ₅	25	16-68	21-48	17-41	9-28	

n.d: not detected

- Due to the lack of a vegetative cover and the particle size of the phosphogypsum tailings aerial transportation and deposition of fine particles occurs on surrounding soils. Dry ash analysis of plants grown spontaneously on the dumps showed elevated concentration of heavy metals (ppm): Pb:500-5000, Zn:1400-3000, Cu:700-3000 and Ra-226:50-370 Bq/kg.
- Solubilisation of heavy elements occurs also from the cinders dump and causes pollution of the surrounding soils.
- Decant waters which are very often discharged to the Black Sea without any neutralisation are characterised by acidic-neutral pH values and contain elevated concentrations of cadmium, fluorine, sulphates, phosphates and Th-234.

Baia

- Baia sulphidic tailings show a considerable potential for acidic water generation. Also, a great number of microbial communities involved in metals solubilisation and biosorption processes was isolated from the tailings dumps and from decant waters.
- Their TCLP toxicity and their bioavailable fractions are considered elevated in terms of iron, zinc and copper.
- The lack of a vegetative cover causes solubilisation of heavy metals, which is favoured by the local weather conditions. In addition aerial transportation of fine particles contaminates surrounding soils.
- Decant waters contain elevated concentration of cadmium.

Table III: Characterisation of Romanian tailings

Romanian	Navodari	Na-	Baia	Somova	Rosia
----------	----------	-----	------	--------	-------

	<i>Standards for soils</i> <i>mg/kg</i>	Phosphogyp- sum <i>mg/kg</i>	Navodari Cinders <i>mg/kg</i>	tailings <i>mg/kg</i>	tailings <i>mg/kg</i>	Poeni tailings <i>mg/kg</i>
S		177300	10000	29000	0	10300
Ca		175500	8650	3500	18300	
S(SO ₄ ²⁻)		177300		27400		
Fe		2350	480070	66100	13300	
F		1100				38000
Cd		4.5				
Al		22	4030	5990	19700	8000
Pb		34.5	2540	525	895	200
Zn		75	1730	130	1010	
As		50	2010			1300
Cu		55	1540	715	75	8800
Mg		77.5	1800	1750	46900	
P ₂ O ₅		22.9				
U	2-8	15				
V		1				
Th-232 (Bq/kg)		12.4				
Th-234 (Bq/kg)		53.4				
Ra-226 (Bq/kg)	10-80	475				
Pb-210 (Bq/kg)		442				
Insoluble		5800	180600	748600	743600	
paste pH		4.05-6.0	2.6	2.37	6.48	
NNP (kg CaCO ₃ /t)		-10	-28	-90.6		
			Fe	Pb	Zn	Cu
	Phosphogyp- sum	0.2	0	0.11	0.07	
TCLP Toxicity (ppm)	Cinders	0.13	0	5.95	2.38	
	Baia	8.13	0	1.61	4.42	
	Somova	0.3	0	6.08	2.77	
	Phosphogyp- sum	424	0	8.7	25.8	
Bioavailable frac- tion (mg/kg)	Cinders	5.2	0	4.9	0	
	Baia	40.7	0	21.4	15	
	Somova	6.1	56	40.5	2.4	
Particle size analysis (mm)		Phosphogyp- sum	Cinders	Baia	Somova	
+0.16		10	16	50	61	
-0.16+0.08		58	55	36	27	
-0.08		32	29	14	12	
Mineralogical phases	Navodari phosphogypsum: gypsum Navodari cinders: magnetite, maghemite, quartz Baia: quartz, hydroniumjarosite, kornelite, gypsum Somova: quartz, feldspar, chlorite, illite, dolomite					

Rosia Poeni: pyrite, chalcopyrite, feldspar, silica

Somova

- Tailings are characterised by neutral paste pH and elevated concentrations of carbonates and other acid consuming materials, therefore they exhibit no potential for acid generation.
- Their TCLP toxicity is considered elevated only for zinc and copper and their bioavailable fraction is considered elevated for iron, lead, zinc and copper.

Table IV: Characterisation of leachates in Romanian sites

	<i>Romanian Standards for surface waters (mg/l)</i>	Navodari decant water (mg/l)	Baia decant water (mg/l)	Somova Lake (mg/l)	Rosia Poeni leachates (mg/l)
Fe		0-7			2900-4400
Cd	0.003	0-29	5.02	0.24	
Al		0-6.5			
Zn	0.03	0-1	0.06	0.05	90
Cu	0.05	0-0.5			165-500
Ca	200	290-604	106	48.1	23-134
Mg		30-85	23.8	13.7	300-500
Pb (ppb)	50	0-4			0-660
F		105-207			
PO ₄ ³⁻		60-1270			
SO ₄ ²⁻		1100-1720			20000-25200
V		0-0.4			
U	0.021	0.027			
Pb-210 (Bq/l)		1			
Ra-226 (Bq/l)	0.088	0.01			
Th-234 (Bq/l)		7.5			
K-40 (Bq/l)		6.3			
pH	6.5-8.6	2.75-5.4	5.75	6.09	2.2-2.4
Eh (mV)		394-150	303	280	440-598

- The existence of several microbial communities in the dumps and in the lake water, at the beginning of the Danube delta, might cause some solubilisation of heavy metals but this solubilisation cannot be quantified because the water quality in the area is adversely affected by the effluents of several heavy industries.
- Aerial transportation of the tailings causes deposition of fine particles in the water, in an area which is characterised as protected ecosystem.

Rosia Poeni

- Copper tailings contain 4% iron, 1% sulphur and lower concentrations of other heavy metals. The nature of the tailings and the climatic conditions in the area favour dissolution of heavy elements and contamination of the surrounding soils and nearby streams.

- Leachates from the copper dumps entering the main decantation pond are characterised by low pH and high Eh values, indicating strong oxidizing conditions, and high concentration of iron, copper, zinc and sulphates. Leachates from the main decantation pond with a pH 4.5 flow through a long and narrow valley at a rate of 400 litres per second over a distance of 2 km and contaminate Aries river.

5. RISK ASSESSMENT

Introduction - Methodology

A risk assessment was performed to assess the environmental risks associated with mining wastes at case study sites in Bulgaria and Romania (Knight Piesold, 1997). The aim of the assessment exercise was to provide a scoping study to identify the targets and objectives for research into preventative and remedial methods of mine waste rehabilitation.

The risk assessment was based on site characterisation data. When data was not considered to be sufficiently comprehensive for a full evaluation of the risks, a qualitative and subjective risk assessment has been undertaken based on the available information, and where necessary stated assumptions. It is also intended that the risk assessment exercise be used to identify where important gaps in environmental characterisation exist, to enable updating and review as additional data become available.

Table V. Risk Assessment Terminology

Term	Definition
Hazard	A property or situation that in particular circumstances could lead to harm.
Consequences	The adverse effects of harm as a result of realising the hazard which causes the quality of human health or the environment to be impaired in the short or longer term.
Probability of consequences	The assessment of the probability that an identified hazard will reach a target in sufficient concentration (or leading to sufficient exposure) to cause harm (See 1.4.2 (i)).
Magnitude of consequences	The prediction of the significance of an impact in terms of its magnitude should the hazard reach the target (See 1.4.2 (ii)).
Risk	A combination of the probability, or frequency of occurrence of a defined hazard and the magnitude of the consequences of the occurrence.
Source	A contaminant or potential pollutant which constitutes a hazard.
Receptor (target)	A human, living organism, ecological system or property (including crops or livestock) that may potentially be affected by a contaminant. The assessment of risk to employees (occupational risk assessment) has been excluded from the assessment.
Pathway (pollutant linkage)	Routes or means by or through which the receptor is being or could be exposed to or affected by a contaminant, such as wind, groundwater and surface water.
Harm	Harm includes disease, serious injury or death to humans; irreversible or other adverse change in the functioning of an ecological system; substantial damage to or failure of buildings, plant or equipment; or disease, physical damage or death of livestock or crops.

Source : DOE (1996) and DOE (1995)

Table VI. Methodology for the Risk Assessment

Stage	Method
Hazard identification and assessment	Identify whether a <i>plausible source-pathway-target relationship</i> exists (ie the identification of a <i>hazard</i> source migrating along a <i>pathway</i> and causing potential <i>harm</i> to a <i>target</i>).
Risk assessment	Once a plausible <i>pollutant pathway</i> has been established, the risk is defined by assessing the probability that the hazard will reach the target and the significance of the impact should the hazard reach the target.
Recommendations for further data collection	Recommendations for additional data collection in order to further define the risk.
Risk management	Use the assessed risk to identify appropriate controls.

Source: DOE (1996), DOE (1995), Harris M and Herbert S (1994)

The approach to risk assessment was based on U.K. guidelines (DOE 1996) Environmental Protection Act 1990 Part IIA Contaminated Land - Draft Statutory Guidance on Contaminated Land and DOE (1995) A Guide to Risk Assessment and Risk Management for Environmental Protection), using the terminology and methodology outlined in the following Tables.

Hazards, or potential sources of contamination which may lead to some form of harm on the local environment were identified and evaluated. This was carried out by establishing whether a plausible source-pathway-target relationship existed, such that targets could be exposed to or affected by a hazard.

For each plausible pollutant pathway identified, a risk assessment was undertaken. The risk was evaluated by assessing the probability of the hazard reaching the target as well as assessing the significance of the impact should the hazard reach the target.

The probability that a contaminant will reach a target in sufficient concentration (or leading to sufficient exposure) to cause harm was assessed according to a qualitative scale (DOE 1995) as: *high* (certain or near certain to occur), *medium* (reasonably likely to occur), *low* (seldom likely to occur) and *negligible* (never likely to occur).

Similarly the significance of an impact in terms of its magnitude, should a hazard reach a target was assessed as (DOE 1995): *severe* (human fatality, major injury or illness causing long term disability; a significant change in number or eradication of one or more species including beneficial, endangered or key species; irreparable damage to non-living structures), *moderate* (human injury or illness causing short term disability; a significant change in species population densities but not total eradication of a species (no effect on endangered or beneficial species); damage to structures which are present in limited numbers eg Grade II listed buildings, *mild* (other human injury or illness, some change in species population densities with no negative effects on ecosystem function; damage to commonplace present day structures which could be repaired) and *negligible* (nuisance rather than harm to humans, no significant changes in any species populations or in any ecosystem functions; very slight damage to structures).

The level of risk associated with each pollutant pathway is then assessed by the combination of this probability of consequence with magnitude of consequence as shown in the following table.

Table VII. Risk Assessment

Probability of consequence	Magnitude of Consequences			
	Severe	Moderate	Mild	Negligible
High	High	High	Medium/Low	Near Zero
Medium	High	Medium	Low	Near Zero
Low	High/Medium	Medium/Low	Low	Near Zero
Negligible	High/Medium/Low	Medium/Low	Low	Near Zero

Source: DOE (1995)

Results

The results obtained for the risk assessment of the Bulgarian and Romanian case study sites are presented below. The flow diagrams 3, 4, 5 and 6 illustrate the potential source-pathway-target relationships for each case study site. The risk assessment undertaken for each of these pathways is summarised in Tables VIII and IX for Vromos Bay and in Tables X, XI and XII for the Romanian sites Navodari, Somova and Baia.

The results of the risk assessment were used to select appropriate targets for research efforts by focusing on high and medium risk pathways as priority areas. In addition, this risk evaluation was also used as a basis for site selection.

From the above analysis it is concluded that the major risks for each side are:

Vromos Bay

- increased radiation levels for humans and livestock through the radioactive decay
- surface drainage which deteriorates surface water quality and affects humans, crops and livestock as well as freshwater ecosystems and the Black Sea

Table VIII: Summary Risk Assessment for the Operational Tailings Facility, Vromos Bay

Source - Pathway - Target			Risk Assessment			
Source	Hazard	Pathway	Target	Probability	Magnitude	Risk
Operational Tailings Facility	Elevated conc. of selected metals and radionuclides	Wind erosion → increased atmospheric dust levels → inhalation	Humans	Low	Mild	Low
		Wind erosion → increased atmospheric dust levels → deposition on agricultural land	Crops	Medium	Moderate	Medium
		Wind erosion → increased atmospheric dust levels → deposition on agricultural land → bioaccumulation	Humans and livestock	Medium	Mild	Low
		Seepage → groundwater quality → potable water abstraction	Humans	Medium	Moderate	Medium
		Surface drainage → surface water quality	Freshwater ecosystems	Medium	Moderate	Medium
		Surface drainage → surface water quality → abstraction for crops and livestock	Crops and livestock	Medium	Moderate	Medium
		Radioactive decay → increased radiation levels	Humans	Low	Severe	High/medium
		Seepage and surface drainage → groundwater and surface water → Black Sea quality	Marine ecosystem	Low	Mild	Low
		Seepage and surface drainage → groundwater and surface water → Black Sea quality → bathing	Humans	Low	Negligible	Near Zero

Table IX: Summary Risk Assessment for the Beach Tailings, Vromos Bay

Source - Pathway - Target				Risk Assessment		
Source	Hazard	Pathway	Target	Probabil- ity	Magni- tude	Risk
Beach Tailings	Elevated conc. of se- lected metals and radionu- clides	Wind erosion → increased atmospheric dust levels → inhalation	Humans	Low	Mild	Low
		Wind erosion → increased atmospheric dust levels → deposition on agricultural land	Crops	Medium	Moderate	Medium
		Wind erosion → increased atmospheric dust levels → deposition on agricultural land → bioaccumulation	Humans and livestock	Medium	Mild	Low
		Radioactive decay → increased radiation levels	Humans	Low	Severe	High/ medium
		Erosion and leaching → Black Sea quality	Marine ecosystem	Medium	Moderate	Medium
		Erosion and leaching → Black Sea quality → bathing	Humans	Medium	Moderate	Medium

- wind erosion which causes deposition of fine particles containing heavy metals and radionuclides on crops
- solubilisation of heavy metals and radionuclides which affect surface water quality and crops

Table X: Summary Risk Assessment for the Navodari site

Source - Pathway - Target				Risk Assessment		
Source	Hazard	Pathway	Target	Probabil- ity	Magni- tude	Risk
Phospho- gypsum and pyrite cinders	Elevated conc. of selected metals and radionuclides	Wind erosion → increased atmospheric dust levels → inhalation	Humans	Medium	Modearte	Medium
		Wind erosion → increased atmospheric dust levels → deposition on agricultural land	Crops	Medium	Modearte	Medium
		Wind erosion → increased atmospheric dust levels → deposition on agricultural land → bioaccumulation	Humans	Medium	Mild	Low
		Radioactive decay → increased radiation levels	Humans	Low	Mild	Low
		Seepage → groundwater quality → portable water abstraction	Humans	Medium	Modearte	Medium
		Surface drainage → surface water quality	Freshwater ecosystems	Medium	Modearte	Medium
		Surface drainage → surface water quality → bioaccumulation	Humans	Low	Negligible	Near zero
		Surface drainage → surface water quality → abstraction for portable supply	Humans	Low	Negligible	Near zero
		Surface drainage → surface water quality → abstraction for crops and livestock	Crops and livestock	Low	Negligible	Near zero
		Seepage and surface drainage → droundwater and surface water → Black Sea quality	Marine ecosystem	Low	Negligible	Low
		Seepage and surface drainage → groundwater and surface water → Black Sea quality → bathing	Humans	Low	Negligible	Near zero

Navodari

- inhalation of dust by residents as well as deposition of dust on agricultural lands
- contamination of groundwater abstraction for potable supply and contamination of ecosystems in local streams and the Black Sea
- solubilisation of heavy metals and anions from phosphogypsum stacks and pyritic cinders dump and contamination of surface streams and surrounding soils

Baia

- inhalation of dust by residents as well as deposition of dust on agricultural lands
- surface drainage which deteriorates surface water quality and affects humans, crops and livestock

Somova

- deterioration of surface water quality in an area located at the start of the extended Danube Delta which is regarded as a protected ecosystem
- contamination of surface water used for irrigation through increased atmospheric dust levels

6. PROPOSED REHABILITATION STRATEGY

From the above mentioned analysis it is concluded that the areas which pose the higher risk to the ecosystems in both countries and endanger the quality of the Black sea are: Vromos bay in Bulgaria and Navodari and Baia in Romania.

The proposed soil remediation technologies for Vromos bay can be classified in two groups: (a) stabilisation techniques, aiming at converting the contaminants to low solubility, mobility and bioavailability forms; and (b) leaching techniques, aiming at removing the contaminants from the soils. Stabilisation can be effected by mixing the soil with various inorganic and organic wastes, as phosphate rock, fly ash, biological sludge, compost and saw dust. Soil toxicity can be reduced below the TCLP regulatory limit with additions of phosphates, fly ash and biological sludge; the immobilisation mechanisms responsible for stabilisation with phosphates are the formation of highly insoluble phosphate compounds, with fly ash the precipitation of metal hydroxides because of the pH increase and with biological sludge the complexation of the metal ions on the free radicals of the organic matter.

As opposed to stabilisation that leaves the heavy metals in the soil in non-toxic forms, removal of the heavy metals from soils by leaching techniques (e.g leaching with citric acid, Na₂-EDTA, Ca-EDTA and HCl-CaCl₂) is a permanent and radical, albeit expensive, long-term solution. The key factors for successful implementation of leaching processes are: efficient removal of the metals to meet regulatory criteria for the treated soils, minimisation of liquid and solid effluents and compliance with environmental discharge regulations, and an affordable cost (Kontopoulos 1996c, Papassiopi 1996). The establishment of a wetland on the other hand seems to offer a low cost and maintenance free solution for the treatment and purification of the leachates entering Vromos bay, as seen from the improved quality of the waters in the natural wetland already existing on site. Before establishing such a wetland a complete study of the decontamination reactions occurring in a wetland should be conducted in a semi-pilot and laboratory scale.

The proposed rehabilitated option for the phosphogypsum dumps in Navodari is the application of a vegetative cover with an overburden cap which will reduce erosion and aerial transfer of fine particles, improve surface runoff quality, promote phosphogypsum dump use as a habitat and improve aesthetics.

Table XI: Summary Risk Assessment for the Baia Site

Source - Pathway - Target				Risk Assessment		
Source	Hazard	Pathway	Target	Probabil- ity	Magni- tude	Risk
Complex sulphidic ore tailings	Elevated conc. of selected metals, potential for acid generation	Wind erosion→increased atmospheric dust levels→inhalation	Humans	Medium	Moderate	Medium
		Wind erosion→increased atmospheric dust levels→deposition on agricultural land	Crops	Medium	Moderate	Medium
		Wind erosion→increased atmospheric dust levels→deposition on agricultural land→bioaccumulation	Humans	Medium	Negligible	Near zero
		Seepage→groundwater quality→portable water abstraction	Humans	Medium	Moderate	Medium
		Surface drainage→surface water quality	Freshwater ecosystems	Medium	Moderate	Medium
		Surface drainage→surface water quality→bioaccumulation	Humans	Low	Negligible	Near zero
		Surface drainage→surface water quality→abstraction for crops and livestock	Crops and Livestock	Medium	Moderate	Medium
		Seepage and surface drainage→groundwater and surface water→Black Sea quality	Marine ecosystem	Low	Mild	Low
		Seepage and surface drainage→groundwater and surface water→Black Sea quality→bathing	Humans	Low	Negligible	Near zero

Table XII: Summary Risk Assessment for Somova site

Source - Pathway - Target				Risk Assessment		
Source	Hazard	Pathway	Target	Probabil- ity	Magni- tude	Risk
Baryte and complex sulphidic ore tails	Elevated conc. of selected metals, potential for acid generation	Wind erosion→increased atmospheric dust levels→inhalation	Humans	Medium	Moderate	Medium
		Wind erosion→increased atmospheric dust levels→deposition on agricultural land	Humans	Low	Negligible	Near Zero
		Wind erosion→increased atmospheric dust levels→deposition on agricultural land→bioaccumulation	Humans	Medium	Negligible	Near Zero
		Seepage→groundwater quality→portable water abstraction	Humans	Low	Mild	Low
		Surface drainage→surface water quality	Freshwater ecosystems	High	Moderate	High
		Surface drainage→surface water quality→bioaccumulation	Humans	Low	Negligible	Near Zero
		Surface drainage→surface water quality→abstraction for portable supply	Humans	Low	Moderate	Medium/ Low
		Surface drainage→surface water quality→abstraction for crops and livestock	Crops and livestock	Low	Mild	Low
		Seepage and surface drainage→groundwater and surface water→Black Sea quality	Marine ecosystem	Low	Negligible	Near Zero
		Seepage and surface drainage→groundwater and surface water→Black Sea quality→bathing	Humans	Low	Negligible	Near Zero

Since phosphogypsum dumps are characterised by residual acidity (mainly due to phosphoric and sulphuric acids and secondary reaction products such as hydrofluoric and hydrofluorosilicic acids), nutrient deficiency, low nutrient holding capacity and tendency for caking and crust formation laboratory glasshouse experiments are conducted in order to study: the reduction of acidity with the use of limestone-dolomite, the effect of the addition of phosphatic clay, sewage sludge and several other amendments as nutrient sources as well as for the reduction of acidity and the establishment of the proper native plant species which can grow on these specific environments.

A soil cover with the addition of some alkaline amendments could be established for the remediation of the pyritic cinders dump and the sulphidic tailing dams in Baia. Alkaline amendments will substantially reduce the potential of the sulphidic tailings to produce acidic waters. The function of the soil is to temporarily store rain water and return it later to the atmosphere via evapotranspiration. A second function is to isolate the toxic tailings from the environment so as to eliminate wind erosion and dusting. It is expected that the cover will inhibit the water to infiltrate into the tailings and react to produce acidity; however, in case of localised failure, the infiltrating water will enter into a cycle of oxidation-neutralisation-precipitation reactions leading to the formation of a hard-pan that will cement the tailings together in a low-permeability layer hindering further infiltration.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The main sources of pollution that are currently directly or indirectly affect the quality of the water in the Black Sea, at the areas of Vromos Bay, in Bulgaria, Navodari and Baia close to Constanta, and Somova close to the Danube Delta in Romania were identified and characterised; they were the flotation tailings dam, the beach tailings and the leachates in Vromos Bay, the phosphogypsum tailings, the pyritic cinders and the decant waters in Navodari, the sulphidic tailings in Baia and the baryte and complex sulphidic tailings in Somova.

Risk analysis based on the source-pathway-target principle showed that all pollution sources constitute, to a higher or lesser extent, a serious hazard for humans, soils and freshwater ecosystems in the area.

Based on the above findings, a rehabilitation strategy is proposed for all affected areas, aiming at deactivating the pollution sources and rehabilitating the contaminated areas with preventative and remedial actions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

All partners would like to greatly acknowledge the financial support of the European Commission under the Copernicus project entitled "Marine pollution in the Black Sea due to mining activities: risk assessment, development of preventive and remedial actions", Contract No: ERB-IC15-CT96-0114.

REFERENCES

1. Brodie, G.A. (1993). Staged, aerobic constructed wetlands to treat acid drainage: Case history of Fabius Impoundment 1 and overview of the Tennessee Valley Authority's Program, in *Constructed Wetlands for Water Quality Improvement*, ed. G.A. Moshiri, Lewis Publishers, p.p.157-165.
2. Davison, J. (1993). Successful acid mine drainage and heavy metal site bioremediation, in 12, p.p. 167-170.
3. DOE (1995) *A Guide to Risk Assessment and Risk Management for Environmental Protection*, U.K
4. DOE (1996) *Environmental Protection Act 1990 Part IIA Contaminated Land-Draft Statutory Guidance on Contaminated Land*, U.K
5. Harris M and Herbert S (1994) *ICE Design and Practice Guides Contaminated Land Investigation, Assessment and Remediation*, Institution of Civil Engineers, U.K
6. Knight Piesold Ltd. (1997) Risk assessment, EC COPERNICUS Project Report
7. Komnitsas K. (1994) Constructed wetlands: A general overview, *Mineral Wealth*, 92, p.p. 39-54.
8. Kontopoulos A., Komnitsas A., Xenidis A., Mylona E., Adam K. (1996a). Rehabilitation of the flotation tailings dam in Lavrion. Part I. Environmental characterisation and development studies, Technology for the Mining Industry, *Conference Proceedings* (M.A. Sanchez, F. Vegara, and S.H. Castro, Eds.), University of Concepcion, Concepcion-Chile.
9. Kontopoulos, A. (1997). Acid mine drainage, genesis and control. In: S.H. Castro et al., eds: *Effluent treatment in the mining industry*. University of Concepcion-Chile.
10. Kontopoulos, A., Komnitsas, K., Xenidis A. (1996b). Rehabilitation of the flotation tailings dam in Lavrion. Part II. Field application, Technology for the Mining Industry, *Conference Proceedings* (M.A. Sanchez, F. Vegara, and S.H. Castro, Eds.), University of Concepcion, Concepcion-Chile.
11. Kontopoulos, A., Komnitsas, K., Xenidis, A., Papassiopi, N. (1995) Environmental characterisation of the sulphidic tailings in Lavrion, *Minerals Engineering*, 8(10), p.p 1209-1219
12. Kontopoulos, A., Papassiopi, N. and Theodoratos, P. (1996c). Rehabilitation of soils contaminated by heavy metals. *Ecological Summit 96*, Copenhagen, Denmark, 19-23 August 1996.
13. Papassiopi, N., Tambouris, S. and Kontopoulos, A. (1996). Evaluation of EDTA for lead removal from calcareous contaminated soils, submitted for publication to *Water, Air and Soil Pollution*.

Fig. 1: Vromos Bay, in Bulgaria

Fig. 3: Source-pathway-target relationships for Vromos Bay

Fig. 4: Source-pathway-target relationships for Navodari

Fig.5: Source-pathway-target relationships for Baia

Fig.6: Source-pathway-target relationships for Somova

